

**TOXICITY INDUCED BY ANIMALS AND BIRDS: PRINCIPLES OF AYURVEDIC
MANAGEMENT****Vaishali Rameshwar Hajare***

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda classifies poisons according to their source into Sthavara Visha, or plant and mineral based poisons, and Jangama Visha, or animal based poisons. For example, snakes produce venom that is considered Jangama Visha, as do various insects, the Akhu, Lutha, Vruschika, Ucchitinga, Manduka and Kanabha, etc. Many types of animal and insect poisons also fall under this classification, including Makshika, because all these harmful substances originate from living organisms. Ayurveda manages the symptoms associated with poisoning using various approaches which includes Aushadha, Panchakarma, Vishaghna lepa and supportive rituals. The use of Agada Kalpa along with lifestyle and dietary adjustments also help to support this process. This article presents a summary of both Ayurvedic concepts regarding the types of toxins produced by animals and birds and shows how Ayurveda treats the effects of these toxins on the human body.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Agadatantra, Visha Chikitsa, Jangama Visha, Sthavara Visha.**INTRODUCTION**

Agadatantra is a branch of Ayurveda that covers many different forms of Visha and how these poisons will have an impact on people, as well as how to treat a person who has become poisoned. Agadatantra divides poisons into two categories: Sthavara Visha and Jangama Visha. The Chaturvimshati Upakrama is the list of different ways to treat someone who has been poisoned by using drugs, and some of these ways are through treatment based on herbs, plants and minerals, and through using herbal remedies to help the body remove toxins from the bloodstream. According to Ayurveda, various types of poison affect various parts or systems of the body; therefore, to best treat a patient, therapeutic guidance is determined by the particular site of involvement.^[1-3]

Visha & Dosha

Clinical presentation with Jangama Visha depends on the type of poison involved. Poison from Ucchitinga and scorpion primarily aggravates Vata Dosha, while poison from Keeta will elicit features of Vata and Pitta

aggravation. Conversely, the poisonous effect of Kanabha is present with symptoms that demonstrate Kapha vitiation. As is indicated by the clinical manifestations of poisoning, the predominant Dosha is the major component of the manifestation of that particular poison. If the poison predominate Vata it will be manifested as the pain located in the cardiovascular area, Stambha, Sira Ayama and Asthi-Parva Ruk. If the poison has a predominant Pitta Dosha, it will manifest as Sanjna Nasha, Ushna Shwasa, Hrid Daha, Katuka Aasya and Damshavat Aavarana. The symptoms of poison associated with Kapha include the presence of Chardi, Arochaka, Hrillasa, Utklesha, Gaurava and lethargy. With the involvement of all three Doshas, a sudden onset of severe symptoms such as pain, burning, swelling, and systemic disturbance occurs.^[4-6]

Symptoms of Jangama Visha

✓ Snake bite produces localized swelling and systemic signs of Vata vitiation, yellowish skin changes around the bite, unctuousness and pallor.

- ✓ *Keeta Visha* as external manifestations of *Dushi Visha* consists of red, black and brownish skin discolouration, *Kandu*, *Daha* and *Visarpa*. *Pranahara Keeta* presents with swelling, bleeding, faintness, pain, shortness of breath and extreme thirst.
- ✓ *Lutha Visha* produces action from the bite that resembles burned skin that results in suppuration and oedema. In cases of greater severity, skin lesions will typically demonstrate the shades of black, red and yellow. Patients may experience *Shwasa*, *Daha*, *Hikka* and *Shiro Graha*.
- ✓ *Akhu Visha* presents with pale bleeding from bite wounds, *Mandalani*, *Jwara*, *Aruchi* and *Loma Harsha*. As it progresses, *Akhu Visha* causes *Murcha*, *Vaivarnya*, *Shabda Ashruti* and *Asrk Chardi*.
- ✓ *Vruschika Visha* cause exceptional burning and pricking pain, and when they are severe, possible temporary loss of eyesight, or the senses of smell or taste, decaying muscle, and in severe cases, can result in death.
- ✓ *Kanabha* Poison has several different symptoms including *Visarpa*, *Shwayathu*, *Shula*, *Jwara* and *Chardi*.
- ✓ Symptoms of *Manduka Visha* include excessive edema, anxiety, a yellowish tint to the skin, *Chardi* and *Nidra*.
- ✓ Fish poisoning is associated with *Daha*, *Shopha*, *Ruja*, *Kandu*, *Shotha*, *Jwara* and *Murcha*.
- ✓ Poisoning from mosquitos is associated with *Kandu*, *Shotha*, *Manda Vedana* and *Jwara*.
- ✓ *Makshika Visha* is represented by small reddish bumps on the skin, brownish discharge from ulcerated areas, burning sensations, *Murchha* from elevated temperatures and blistering on the surface of the affected areas.^[5-7]

Chikitsa of Visha

Management of poisoning in Ayurveda is based on the principles of *Agada Tantra* and it includes methods for detoxification, use of antidotes and promoting the restoration of healthy body function. The goal of this integrated system is both to eliminate the toxic substances and to restore the body's normal function and promote healing. The method of treating poisoning is depends upon various factors as mentioned in **Figure 1**.

Table 1: Therapies according to the sources of toxicity.

TYPE OF VISHA	AYURVEDIC DRUGS
<i>Sarpa Visha</i>	<i>Pippali</i> , <i>Nagara</i> , <i>Jatamamsi</i> , <i>Kunkuma</i> , <i>Patra</i> , <i>Rajani</i> , <i>Nata</i> , <i>Chandana</i> , <i>Manohshila</i> , <i>Vyaghra Nakha</i>
<i>Keeta Visha</i>	<i>Ksheeri Vriksha</i> , <i>Chandana</i> , <i>Ushira</i> , <i>Sirisha</i> , <i>Nata</i> , <i>Patala</i> , <i>Udichya</i>
<i>Loota Visha</i>	<i>Kusumbha</i> , <i>Go-Danta</i> , <i>Svarna-Kshiri</i> , <i>Danti</i> , <i>Trivrit</i> , <i>Saindhava</i>
<i>Vrischika Visha</i>	Juice of citrus fruits, <i>Shankhini</i> , <i>Sunthi</i> , <i>Karanja</i> , <i>Sheshashana</i>
<i>Matsya Visha</i>	<i>Sunthi</i> , <i>Pippali</i> and <i>Maricha</i>

Figure 1: Factors affecting treatment of poisoning conditions.

Type of toxins and amount of toxin, *Prakriti* of the individual, the compatibility of the toxin with the individual, the level of emergency required to prevent adverse health effects in the person experiencing the poisoning, etc. are major factors affecting treatment strategy while managing poisoning conditions.

Treatment for *Vata* types of poisons focuses on sweetening agents, warming therapies, an appropriate diet and other supporting methods to counteract the acute effects of the poison on the body, for *Pitta* types of poisons, the approach is to use cooling or cold applications, administer *Stambhana* medicines to restrict the rapid movement of fluids, and eliminate the poison. For *Kapha* types of poisons, treatment may include scraping, cutting or puncture, application of heat, and purging therapies to overcome heaviness and stagnation.^[6-8]

Each treatment approach is specific to the organ affected by the poison. In the case of *Hrudgata Visha*, where the *Jangama Visha* produces burning sensations in the heart, emesis should be initiated first, followed by the *Samsarjana Krama*. *Shirogata Visha* is treated by scraping the scalp and administering products made from a rooster's and a crow's meat and blood. For *Chakshugata Visha*, the treatment includes *Anjana* with *Pippali*, *Maricha*, *Kshara*, *Vacha*, *Saindhava* and *Shigrū*. For *Kanthagata Visha* (poisons affecting the throat), the treatment is a combination of *Feronia limonia*, sugar and honey.

Similarly the **Table 1**; summarizes types of drug therapies recommended according to the various source of toxicity.^[7-9]

The *Chaturvimshati Upakramas* (twenty-four *Upakramas*) neutralizes; break down; and, ultimately eliminate toxins through restoring total body balance. The *Chaturvimshati Upakramas* are applicable to plant, animal, artificial and chronic residual toxin exposures. These approaches help to manage chronic conditions and delay emergency of acute & severe toxicity.^[8-10]

CONCLUSION

Agadatantra provides an organized framework to assist healthcare professionals in recognizing, reading, and handling different types of poisons using Ayurveda's understanding of toxicology. In *Agadatantra*, poisons are further divided into two main categories (*Sthavara* and *Jangama*), so that healthcare professionals can recognize that different types of toxic substances will afflict patients in different ways based on their *Dosha* profile. Furthermore, all *Jangama Visha* has been thoroughly documented in classical Ayurvedic literature by assessing the clinical signs and symptoms produced by *Jangama Visha*, which allows for the identification of specific patterns of toxicity. The combination of therapeutic measures, based on the *Chaturvimshati Upakramas* is designed to eliminate toxins through apoptosis and detoxification; help to restore normal physiological functioning.

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